

Impact of social media on the firm's knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation: The role of business analytics talent

Paper published in
Journal of the Association for Information Systems
(JAIS)

Full citation to this publication:

Castillo, A., Benitez, J., Llorens, J., & Braojos, J. (2021). Impact of social media on the firm's knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation: The role of business analytics talent. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 22(5), 1472-1508.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17705/1jais.00700>

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Abstract

Social media are one of the most disruptive technologies in the execution of the firm's digital business transformation strategies. Does the firm's ability to use social media affect the firm's proficiency in exploring and exploiting knowledge? What could be the role of business analytics talent in this equation? We study theoretically and empirically these cutting-edge research questions. Our proposed research model argues that social media capability enables the development of knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, and business analytics talent exerts a positive reinforcing role in the impact of social media on knowledge exploration. We tested the proposed research model with a secondary dataset from a sample of U.S. firms. The proposed research model was empirically tested using PLS path modeling. After running a robustness test by estimating eight alternatives/competing models, the empirical analysis shows that social media capability is positively related with both knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, but with a stronger effect on knowledge exploration. Moreover, business analytics talent plays a positive moderator role on the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration. This study contributes to the IS research by: 1) introducing, developing, and operationalizing the concepts of social media capability and business analytics talent; and 2) theoretically arguing and empirically showing the pivotal role of social media capability in exploring new knowledge, and the complementary role of business analytics talent. Our study also provides several critical lessons learned for top executives and propose some promising future avenues for IS research.

Keywords: Social media capability, knowledge exploration, knowledge exploitation, business analytics talent, the business value of social media, ADANCO.

1. Introduction

Social media are one of the most disruptive technologies in the execution of the firm's digital business transformation strategies (Benitez et al., 2020a; Wessel et al., forthcoming). However, our theoretical understanding of this new corporate phenomenon is in its initial stages (Benitez et al., 2018a). Social media can play a key role in collecting, monitoring, and analyzing data to generate business value (He et al., 2015). Social media platforms are considered one of the most popular online communication tools and source of information, acting as facilitators of knowledge and a potential source of firm performance (Benitez et al., 2018a; Chai et al., 2011; Krancher et al., 2018; Leonardi, 2014; Luo et al., 2015). For example, firms can use social media (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, corporate blogs) to build awareness about their products and initiatives and to test them by collecting opinions, impressions, and ideas from customers (Dong and Wu, 2015). As an illustrative example, Lay's (a potato chip manufacturer) ran a campaign in social media (Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram) called "Do us a flavor." This campaign aimed to innovate about the next potato chip flavor, collecting ideas from their customers. Four finalist flavors were sold provisionally, and customers voted in social media for the best one, being Southern Biscuits and Gravy flavor eventually sold. Thus, social media provide a vast amount of customer, competitor, and supplier data that can be leveraged by the firm to innovate and improve firm performance (Aral et al., 2013; Benitez et al., 2018a). Based on the organizational capabilities-based theory, this study introduces, develops, and focuses on social media capability, which refers to the firm's ability to use and leverage external social media to execute business activities. Firms with a high level of social media capability may convert social media in a golden source of data, changing how firms exchange information (Benitez et al., 2018a; French et al., 2017).

Social media may have the potential to enable firms to analyze and examine new knowledge (i.e., knowledge exploration), and recombine existing knowledge (i.e., knowledge exploitation). Knowledge exploration refers to the learning obtained from the process of acquiring/creating, sharing, and storing new knowledge. Knowledge exploitation is the learning process of

assimilating, reusing, reinterpreting, applying, and leveraging new/existing knowledge (Gupta et al., 2006; March, 1991). However, despite the suggested potential value, how firms leverage external social media to explore knowledge and exploit knowledge needs further development and empirical testing.

Generating and collecting social data (i.e., data from social media) might not be enough to make efficient use of information. The value creation from social data requires knowledge understanding. Monitoring, analyzing, and identifying relevant social media-based information is critical in transforming information into business gains. Ransbotham et al. (2015) suggested that using social data effectively may be critical to support business activities. The process of changing data into valuable insights to support business activities is called “business analytics” (Chen et al., 2012; Holsapple et al., 2014; Zhang et al., forthcoming). Business analytics refers to the support of decision making and problem resolution into the firms through two main capabilities: “speed to insight” (i.e., how fast firms can transform social data into useful insights), and “pervasive use” (i.e., deep usage of business analytics across the firm) (Wixom et al., 2013). In this sense, firms face the challenge of attracting, hiring, developing, and retaining business analytics talent to transform social data into valuable insights for supporting business activities. This paper focuses on business analytics talent. As a scarce and valuable resource, business analytics talent may explain the variation in performance among contemporary firms (Edwards, 2020; Ransbotham et al., 2015). Business analytics talent is the firm’s talent in effectively applying business analytics at the firm level by transforming data into valuable insights for supporting business activities (Ransbotham et al., 2015). Firms with business analytics talent can effectively perform business analytics to turn analytical insight into business actions. Firms effectively performing business analytics go from descriptive analytics to determine what occurred in the past, and what occurs now and why, through predictive analytics to model what will happen in the future, to prescriptive analysis to develop multiple options about the future and help decide what to do (Ransbotham et al., 2015). Given its importance, business analytics talent is a scarce and valuable information

technology (IT) resource that may help firms to build IT wisdom in contemporary firms (Liu et al., 2020). It has been estimated that 2.7 million business analytics jobs will be posted in the U.S. in 2020 (Fenlon and Peters, 2020).

Information Systems (IS) research lacks theory building on how firms perform social media initiatives and how these initiatives may affect a firm's knowledge exploration and exploitation activities (Dong and Wu, 2015; Ngai et al., 2015). Firms may invest in managing social media effectively to acquire and exploit social data to improve their performance. This argument leads to the first research question of this study: 1) Does social media capability enable knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation? This study tries to fill this research gap and answer this question. The effect of social media capability on knowledge exploration may be stronger in those firms that additionally transform social data into new useful social knowledge through business analytics talent (Davenport et al., 2010; Ransbotham et al., 2015). This rationale leads to the second research question of this paper: 2) Can the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration be strengthened when business analytics talent comes into play?

We argue that social media capability can enable firms to explore and exploit knowledge and that firms with more and better business analytics talent can amplify and strengthen the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration. This is the central theoretical proposition of this manuscript. We tested the proposed research model using partial least squares (PLS) path modeling with a secondary dataset on a sample of U.S. firms. After estimating eight alternatives/competing models in the robustness check, the empirical analysis provides substantial support to our central proposition.

This study has several contributions to the field of IS. First, this paper introduces, develops, and operationalizes the concepts of social media capability and business analytics talent by using archival data that can be used in future IS research. Second, this study theoretically argues and empirically shows the pivotal role of social media capability in exploring new knowledge for organizations and the amplifying role of business analytics talent into this equation.

2. Theory and hypotheses

2.1. Organizational capabilities-based theory, IT-enabled organizational capabilities, organizational learning framework, and the complementary resource perspective

The organizational capabilities-based theory suggests that firms design and execute IT and business strategies based on their portfolio of organizational capabilities, which explains the difference in competitiveness among firms (Grant, 1996). Organizational capabilities¹ can be classified into dynamic capabilities (firm's proficiency in adapting its resource base in response to changes in the business environment) (Benitez et al., 2018b; Teece, 2007); operational capabilities (firm's proficiency in solving operational problems and implementing the operations strategy by using interrelated operational routines) (Benitez et al., 2018c; Wu et al., 2010); and dual-purpose capabilities (organizational capabilities that are dynamic and operational capabilities because they can be controlled and exploited at both strategic/corporate and operational level) (Benitez et al., 2018b; Helfat and Winter, 2011). We use the organizational capabilities-based theory to conceptualize social media capability, knowledge exploration, knowledge exploitation and business analytics talent (the key constructs of this study), and to link social media capability to knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation.

The IT-enabled organizational capabilities perspective has emerged as a solid theoretical base in the IS literature to explain the value creation from IT by arguing that IT helps firms to create business value by developing intermediate organizational/process capabilities (Lin et al., forthcoming; Mandrella et al., 2020; Mikalef et al., 2020; Schmiedel et al., 2020). Some of these organizational capabilities are business flexibility (Benitez et al., 2018b; Benitez et al., 2018d; Chen et al., 2017), supply chain management (Ajamieh et al., 2016), corporate entrepreneurship (Chen et al., 2015), new product development (Pavlou and El Sawy, 2006), and knowledge search

¹ Organizational capabilities can be IT capabilities and business capabilities. Business capabilities refer to the non-IT capabilities of the firm. In this sense, companies can develop dynamic, operational, and dual-purpose IT and business capabilities (Benitez et al., 2018b).

and relational search management (Hensen and Dong, 2020). As social media technology is a new type of digital technology, IT-enabled organizational capabilities theory provides a useful conceptual framework to theorize that social media capability enables knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation.

Organizational learning refers to the process in which firms pursue organizational renewal through the creation of knowledge, explaining, and codifying this knowledge, and sharing and transferring this knowledge within the firm to be used, and embedding it through rules and procedures (March, 1991). This study draws from the organizational learning framework, which considers knowledge exploration and exploitation as two firm's learning activities (Gupta et al., 2006). Knowledge exploration is the learning process of acquiring/creating, sharing, and storing new knowledge, while knowledge exploitation is composed by the learning obtained from the process of assimilating, reusing, reinterpreting, applying, and leveraging new/existing knowledge (Gupta et al., 2006; March, 1991). Ambidextrous firms in managing knowledge are those that efficiently achieve exploration and exploitation of knowledge simultaneously for operational purposes (Benitez et al., 2018a; Levinthal and March, 1993; Tushman and O'Reilly, 1996). Achieving simultaneously knowledge exploration and exploitation may help firms to achieve long-term business benefits (Raisch and Birkinshaw, 2008). Despite the importance of understanding how knowledge ambidexterity works, there is a critical difference between a firm's knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation because they require significantly different structures, processes, strategies, capabilities, and cultural values (Dominguez and Massaroli, 2018). In this sense, knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation may have different relationships with other variables such as social media capability, business analytics talent, and firm performance. For example, knowledge exploration is more related to organic structure, flexible systems, autonomy, and improvisation, whereas knowledge exploitation is more related to mechanical structure, rigid systems, control, bureaucracy, and routine (Dominguez and Massaroli, 2018). For all these reasons, this study focuses on the individual impact of social media capability on

knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation instead of examining the effect of social media capability on knowledge ambidexterity. We use the organizational learning framework to conceptualize knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation.

The complementary resource perspective is a theoretical framework that suggests that the complementarity among resources of the firm explains the differential effect in business benefits. Complementarity between resources/capabilities denotes the mutual reinforcing of the resources/capabilities where the presence of a resource/capability allows other resources/capabilities to exert their value (Ennen and Richter, 2010). These complementary relationships may drive the pursuit of more efficient processes, which may differ from the sum of the individual effects considered in isolation (Adegbesan, 2009; Bharadwaj et al., 2007). Our central proposition is that the positive effect of social media capability on knowledge exploration can be amplified if the firm additionally has business analytics talent. We use the complementary resource perspective to explain theoretically how business analytics talent complements social media capability to enable knowledge exploration.

2.2. Impact of social media on organizations and individuals, and opportunities for IS research

Although prior studies in this stream of IS research highlighted the critical role of social media and provided some evidence about its impact on the knowledge sharing of individuals and organizations, there are two research opportunities in the existing literature. First, although the crucial challenge for organizations is to learn how they can develop the ability of effectively selecting, using, and leveraging external social media among changing platforms to scan, learn, and internalize knowledge, it remains rather unclear how companies can develop a social media capability and create business value from this capability. Instead, prior IS research has focused on understanding the knowledge sharing behavior of employees in enterprise social media (Beck et al., 2014; Leonardi, 2014; Neely and Leonardi, 2018; Song et al., 2019), user-generated content and customer engagement to diffuse information through social media (Bapna et al., 2019; Yang

et al., 2019). Prior IS research has also focused on exploring the customer behavior in social media in complaints (Gunarathne et al., 2017) and service (Gunarathne et al., 2018) and knowledge-sharing behavior of bloggers (Chai et al., 2011). Prior IS research has mainly focused on the employee, customer and user, and less in organizations as the main level of analysis (see Table A1 in the appendix). Despite the plausible role the firm's proficiency in using and selecting external social media may play in the exploration of new knowledge and the exploitation of existing knowledge (Chau and Xu, 2012), this research topic is under-theorized in IS research.

Although the firm's business analytics talent may perform a critical role in understanding and acquire new knowledge from big customer data in social media, this plausible effect is not understood well. Instead, prior IS research has focused on the impact of big data analytics capability on competitive performance (Mikalef et al., 2020) and its reinforcing role to create synergies and improves market performance (Dong and Yang, 2020). However, it seems to exist an overemphasis on the analytics software and a minimization of the role of analytics talent and people (Conboy et al., 2020). The goal of our research is to address these research opportunities. First, our study examines the development of social media capability and its impact on the firm's exploration and exploitation of knowledge. Second, we also examine whether and how business analytics talent reinforces the impact of social media capability on knowledge exploration. Figure 1 presents the proposed research model.

Figure 1: Proposed research model

Note: CV: Control variables.

2.3. Conceptualization of key constructs of the study

2.3.1. Social media capability

Social media capability is the firm's ability to purposely use and leverage external social media platforms to execute business activities (Benitez et al., 2018a). This study considers three of the external social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, and corporate blogs) most used by contemporary firms (Culnan et al., 2010). In 2018 89%, 91%, and 53% of the Fortune 500 firms used Facebook, Twitter, and corporate blogs, respectively, for business activities (Barnes et al., 2019). In this sense, social media capability covers three of the most relevant external social media used by firms (Braojos et al., 2019). The development of social media capability is heterogeneous between companies, which suggests that there are companies with a high- and low-developed social media capability. Firms with a high-developed social media capability can engage customers and employees to talk positively about the company's activities, cultural values, and share knowledge. Melia Hotels International (a leading hotel group worldwide) is an example of a company with a high social media capability. Melia has leveraged social media to manage the customer relationship/experience better, improving the digital brand and web traffic from social

media, co-creating knowledge, attracting talent and improving its employer branding.² On the other side, Molson Company (a multinational brewing company) illustrates an example of a company with a low social media capability. Molson Company had a static presence on Facebook in 2007 when it decided to exploit social media potential by launching a Facebook campaign that encouraged university students to post pictures drinking, and it was criticized for promoting such irresponsible drinking, which affected negatively to its corporate reputation (Compeau and Qureshi, 2008).

Recent IS research on IT and knowledge management capabilities has operationalized the concept of IT-enabled capabilities (Joshi et al., 2010; Saldanha et al., forthcoming). For example, Joshi et al. (2010) conceptualized IT-enabled absorptive capacity as the IT contributions to firms' abilities in acquiring, assimilating, transforming, and exploiting knowledge. Saldanha et al. (forthcoming) have operationalized the IT-enabled social integration capacity as the firm's use of IT that fosters social capital through social interaction and connectedness. They also introduced the use of several internal and external IT applications (e.g., wikis, blogs, enterprise social networking sites). We draw on this prior IS research to conceptualize social media capability. However, our concept of social media capability presents unique and original characteristics concerning IT-enabled absorptive capacity and IT-enabled social integration capacity. First, social media capability refers directly and exclusively to the firm's ability to leverage external social media platforms (i.e., a specific type of IT). Second, differently to prior IS research (e.g., Andrade et al., 2018; Saldanha et al., forthcoming), this study does not focus only acquiring or recombining knowledge but on how social media capability affects firm's knowledge exploration (i.e., acquiring/creating, sharing, and storing new knowledge) and knowledge exploitation (i.e., assimilating, reusing, reinterpreting, applying, and leveraging existing knowledge).

² As Gabriel Escarrer (CEO of Melia Hotels International) says: "The influence of social media these days on corporate reputation and firm performance is undebatable. Being active in social media has given us the opportunity to share more and better knowledge on our company, and understanding better our customers and other stakeholders, reinforcing our relationships with them" (Hootsuite, 2020a, p. 4).

2.3.2. Knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation

Knowledge exploration refers to the learning process of experimenting with new knowledge and business opportunities by acquiring/creating, sharing, and storing this new knowledge (March, 1991). Knowledge exploitation refers to the learning process of assimilating, reusing, reinterpreting, applying, and leveraging existing/new knowledge (March, 1991). In prior literature, two theories on the organizational viability coexist to explore and exploit knowledge: as two extremes of a continuum (tradeoffs), or as two independent activities (complementary strategies) (Benitez et al., 2018a; Gupta et al., 2006). As two extremes of a continuum, exploration of new knowledge and the exploitation of existing knowledge are the two extremes of the same continuum (Rosenkopf and McGrath, 2011), which invites specializing/focusing in either exploration or exploitation (March, 1991). A company may be situated in an intermediate position instead of some of the extremes, where the consideration of exploration and exploitation would be of the equilibrium.

As two independent activities, knowledge exploration and exploitation are orthogonal and differentiated by the level of learning (Gupta et al., 2006; He and Wong, 2004). Under this body of literature, companies can pursue both exploration and exploitation of knowledge. Our study draws from this stream of literature to explore how social media capability affects the firm's exploration and exploitation of knowledge. Although they are complementary, as knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation are different, it is rational to think that they may have different relationships with other resources. Therefore, it is both important and necessary to know the different effects of other resources in these two processes. We focus on the interface between business analytics talent, and exploration and exploitation of knowledge-driven by social media capability.

2.3.3. Business analytics talent

Business analytics is a group of people, approaches, organizational procedures, and tools used in combination that convert data into insights for problem recognition and solving within a business situation context (Holsapple et al., 2014; Trkman et al., 2010; Wixom et al., 2013). The notion of

business analytics talent in this study is derived from the work of Ransbotham et al.'s (2015) on analytics talent. We draw on this work to conceptualize and measure business analytics talent. Business analytics talent is a firm's resource that refers to the talent of people on performing business analytics (i.e., high-level analytical skills) to be able to transform data in insights valuable for supporting business activities (Ransbotham et al., 2015). Business analytics talent is conceptually a different construct than social media capability as there are some companies with a high/low social media capability, but they do not have business analytics talent because of the scarcity in the market. Our conceptualization is consistent with recent IS research that investigated big data analytics capability individually and has highlighted its potential value (e.g., Mikalef et al., 2020). However, other IS scholars may be interested in examining the overall IT-enabled information management capability, which it would invite to combine the analysis of both social media and business data analytics under the same concept and theoretical lens (e.g., Andrade and Kathuria, 2014). Our conceptualization of business analytics talent deliberately excludes business analytics talent, and we propose that social media capability can enable firms to explore and exploit knowledge and that firms with more and better business analytics talent can amplify and strengthen the relationship between social media capability and firm's knowledge exploration.³

2.4. Social media capability and knowledge exploration

Social media capability can facilitate knowledge exploration of the firm. Firms can use external social media (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, corporate blogs) to acquire new knowledge from customers, competitors, and suppliers, and to create and share new knowledge with them, thus facilitating the exploration of new knowledge. Firms can use Facebook and Twitter to reach current and potential customers and interact with them to acquire customer knowledge (e.g., customer preferences and

³ We check for the discriminant validity between social media capability and business analytics talent by estimating the heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) (Benitez et al., 2020b). The value of the HTMT between social media capability and business analytics talent is 0.361 (lower than 0.90) and was significantly smaller than 1 (0.499), thus suggesting the existence of clear discriminant validity between these two constructs. These two constructs are both conceptually and statistically different.

feedback on the current firm's products) (Andrade and Kathuria, 2014). These social media can also be leveraged to co-develop new products with customers, creating new product and customer knowledge (Patroni et al., forthcoming; Testa et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2016) and also share knowledge with customers (e.g., communication of new products), thus enabling knowledge exploration. For example, Mercadona (i.e., the leader supermarket chain in Spain) leverages Twitter to acquire new customer knowledge. Based on the knowledge contribution from customers on the Mercadona's Twitter site, Mercadona has discovered the customer complain about the stock out of a product in a store. Mercadona has also leveraged Twitter to discover new customer preferences (e.g., vegan products) faster the direct competitors. Mercadona is another example of a company with high-level social media capability. This example illustrates how a company can leverage Twitter to acquire and create new customer knowledge.

Firms can also use external social media to acquire new knowledge from competitors and co-create new knowledge with their supplier network. Firms can monitor social media (Facebook, Twitter, blogs) of the direct competitors to acquire knowledge on the competitor movements and competitive actions (e.g., a supermarket chain that analyzes the key supplier base of its direct competitors in Twitter) to design their competitive strategy and actions (Andrade and Kathuria, 2014). Finally, the firm's external social media can be used as collaborative platforms to exchange and co-create new products and projects with suppliers, thus enabling the knowledge exploration with the firm's suppliers. Therefore, we hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): There is a positive relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration.

2.5. Social media capability and knowledge exploitation

Social media capability can also positively influence the exploitation of existing knowledge. The firm's proficiency in selecting, using, and leveraging external social media (Facebook, Twitter, corporate blogs) may facilitate the firm to assimilate, reinterpret, reuse, and apply existing knowledge, thus increasing knowledge exploitation. The external social media can serve as

customer and competitor knowledge repositories, which facilitate the knowledge assimilation and reuse (Jarvenpaa and Majchrzak, 2010; Lu et al., 2015). Companies can also use external social media to develop and maintain long-term relationships with current and potential customers, which may collaborate and share knowledge with the firm to reinterpret and apply customer and product knowledge, thus enabling the exploitation of knowledge. For example, Mercadona uses Twitter to exploit existing knowledge. Many tweets had flooded Twitter with requests for easily finding kefir (i.e., a sour drink which contains so-called gut-friendly bacteria). Mercadona applied and leveraged this knowledge to commercialize this product in increasing demand in its stores, which has been acknowledged by its customers. One customer uploaded a Kefir's picture with the following text: "If there is one thing that I like about Mercadona is that they always listen to the customers' suggestions." This example illustrates how the firm-customer interactions in external social media (e.g., Twitter) provide Mercadona "clues" to reinterpret and reuse existing customer and product knowledge, thus facilitating the exploitation of knowledge. We thus hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 2 (H2): There is a positive relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploitation.

2.6. The business value of business analytics talent: The moderator role of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration

We argue that when the firm has talent in business analytics, the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration can be amplified, that is, business analytics talent can play a positive moderator (reinforcing) role in this relationship. Social media facilitate the exploration of a vast amount of new knowledge. However, business analytics talent is required to have a good understanding and to explore this amount of knowledge efficiently (Chau and Xu, 2012). Firms with superior business analytics talent can collect, monitor, analyze, and summarize the vast amount of unstructured new knowledge to create meaningful knowledge quickly and new insights (He et al., 2015), which can be easily stored (i.e., knowledge exploration). Social media data may

be unstructured, subjective, and massive (Chan et al., 2016). The ideas expressed in social media can be easily misunderstood and misapplied (Faraj et al., 2011), which requires firms to use analytical skills to effectively explore knowledge and convert social data into useful and understandable new knowledge. Business analytics talent is pivotal by firms to create and store useful knowledge acquired from external social media. Therefore, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Business analytics talent positively moderates (reinforces and amplifies) the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration.

Table 1 presents a summary of the main arguments of the hypotheses that composes the proposed research model.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Sample

We tested the proposed model with a sample of the 100 small firms included in the 2013 Forbes America's Best Small Companies ranking (in short, the Forbes database). This ranking is composed of the best 100 publicly recognized U.S. small firms with sales under one billion dollars (Benitez et al., 2018a). The firms of our sample came from 30 industries: consulting (18 firms), IT (16 firms), food manufacturing (7 firms), semiconductor manufacturing (6 firms), healthcare (5 firms), chemical (5 firms), and other industries (43 firms).

Prior IS research has contextualized several types of the business value of IT studies on a sample of firms included in well-known rankings (as the ranking used in this study) (e.g., Benitez et al., 2018a; Benitez and Walczuch, 2012; Joshi et al., 2010), which suggests that our decision in using the Forbes database was rational. We focused on this specific ranking for two reasons. First, because small firms have a lower portfolio of financial resources to compete more effectively in the market, leveraging their investments in social media capability and business analytics talent to manage knowledge remains central, as compared with large firms (Benitez et al., 2018a). Second, the majority of prior IS research on social media, and business activities have focused on

large firms (Luo et al., 2013; Kane et al., 2014a). Another distinctive feature of our research is its focus on small firms.

Table 1: Summary of key theoretical arguments of the proposed research model

Hypotheses	Main theoretical arguments	Illustrative example
H1: There is a positive relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration	Firms can use external social media (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, corporate blogs) to acquire new knowledge from customers, competitors, and suppliers, and to create and share new knowledge with them, thus facilitating the exploration of new knowledge. For example, firms can use Facebook and Twitter to reach current and potential customers and interact with them to acquire customer knowledge (e.g., customer preferences and feedback on the current firm's products) (Andrade and Kathuria, 2014)	Nestle UK leveraged external social media (e.g., Facebook) to engage young customers and acquire new ideas to rejuvenate Kit Kat Chunky products. Customers "liked" and voted for different flavors, helping Nestle in the new product development (Mount and Garcia, 2014)
H2: There is a positive relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploitation	The firm's proficiency in selecting, using, and leveraging external social media may facilitate firms to assimilate, reinterpret, reuse, and apply existing knowledge, thus increasing knowledge exploitation. The external social media can serve as customer and competitor knowledge repositories, which facilitate the knowledge assimilation and reuse. Companies can also use external social media to develop and maintain long-term relationships with current and potential customers, which may collaborate and share knowledge with the firm to reinterpret and apply customer and product knowledge, thus enabling the exploitation of knowledge	CaixaBank (a leading Spanish bank) has led the capability of leveraging external social media in the banking industry in Spain. CaixaBank has selected Facebook and Twitter to reuse and apply existing overall knowledge. CaixaBank has leveraged these external social media to develop and maximize customer relationships by providing viral posts on tips on recipes, health, nutrition, and sports to touch families (Gonzalez, 2020)
H3: Business analytics talent positively moderates (reinforces and amplifies) the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration	Firms with superior business analytics talent can collect, monitor, analyze, and summarize the vast amount of unstructured new knowledge to create meaningful knowledge quickly (He et al., 2015), which can be easily stored (knowledge exploration), thus amplifying the effect of social media capability on knowledge exploration	Nestle UK used business analytics talent to develop a business data analytics capability (Mikalef et al., 2020). Nestle used business analytics talent to analyze, text mine and data-mine customer-generated content (big data) and explore patterns of new knowledge (Mount and Garcia, 2014), thus amplifying the impact of social media on knowledge exploration

To check whether our sample meets the minimum required size to examine the effects included in the proposed model, before data collection, we performed a statistical power analysis. Assuming an anticipated medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.150$), to achieve a statistical power of 0.800, five

predictors (i.e., the number of effects received by knowledge exploration), and an alpha of 0.05, the minimum required size for our sample was 91 (Cohen, 1988). As our sample size is 100, there is enough statistical power to estimate the research model.

3.2. Data and operationalization of variables

The data used to measure and test the proposed research model, and testing the robustness models come from nine databases: Facebook, Twitter, and blog firm's site, LexisNexis, Knowledge Management World, U.S. Patent and Trademark Office, Datastream, Forbes, and firms' websites. Thus, the full dataset provides an innovative and unique set of data and measures to test the central proposition of this study.

3.2.1. Specification of the measurement model

A clear distinction can be done between behavioral constructs and design constructs (they are also called artifacts and emergent variables) (Benitez et al., 2020b; Henseler, 2017). While behavioral constructs are usually modeled as a common factor (reflective) models, composite-formative⁴ (in short, composite) should be the preferred choice for modeling artifacts. These artifacts can be understood as theoretically justified constructions that consist of more elementary components (Benitez et al., 2018b; Benitez et al., 2018d). They are human-made objects and concepts that are typically created by executives, staff, or the firm itself, and should be modeled as a composite (Benitez et al., 2020b). The artifact serves as a proxy for the concept under investigation and can be understood as a mix of ingredients (indicators) forming the recipe (artifact) (Benitez et al., 2018b; Henseler, 2015, 2017; Rueda et al., 2017). Composite modeling is the way of estimating artifacts (Benitez et al., 2020b). Based on the above arguments, all the

⁴ Two types of formative measurements exist: composite-formative (artifact) and causal-formative (latent variable). The main differences between them are: 1) in composite measurement the indicators make up the construct, whereas in causal-formative measurement the indicators cause the construct, 2) high correlations among the indicators are common but not required in composite measurement, whereas correlations are not expected in causal-formative measurement, 3) the indicators of composite constructs do not involve measurement error, whereas the indicators of causal-formative constructs have measurement error, and 4) dropping an indicator alters the composite and may change its meaning, whereas dropping an indicator increases the measurement error on the causal-formative constructs (Benitez et al., 2020b; Henseler, 2017).

constructs of this research were considered as artifacts and were modeled as composite. In short, in sake for brevity, we refer to artifacts as composite constructs.

3.2.2. Social media capability

Social media capability is a composite second-order construct composed of three dimensions: Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability (Benitez et al., 2018a; Culnan et al., 2010). We use the firm's social media activities on Facebook, Twitter, and corporate blog(s) because they are a good proxy to evaluate social media capability (Braojos et al., 2019). It is rational to expect that firms develop a social media capability through the experimentation and execution of a high number of social media activities. These social media activities refer to the activities performed by the firm and do not include the posts of the social media users, thus removing the customer engagement metrics from the social media capability measurements. The measurement and conceptualization focus on the firm's social media activities. Facebook, Twitter, and blogs are three of the most relevant external social media used by companies (Benitez et al., 2020a; Culnan et al., 2010). We measured social media capability based on the validated measure scheme of Benitez et al. (2018a) and Benitez et al. (2020a), with data collected in 2014.

Facebook capability: It was evaluated as a composite first-order construct through the following ingredients: number of events, experience, and updates, using information from the Facebook site of the firm. 74% of the firms of the sample had a Facebook site. Where a firm did not have a Facebook site, each of the specific ingredients of Facebook capability was coded as 0. One of these ingredients is the number of events organized on Facebook by the company. Facebook events refer to the number of past and future calendar-based upcoming occasions such as celebrations, meetings, conferences, and showings organized by a company. On average, the firms of the sample organized 5.510 events from the creation of the Facebook firm's site until the data collection period (2014). The second ingredient of Facebook capability was the firm's experience using Facebook. A company probably develops the ability to use and leverage Facebook through experience, trial and error, and experimenting. The experience on Facebook

was measured as the average number of months that the firm had been operating on Facebook from the creation of the Facebook firm's site until 2014, with information collected from the Twopcharts database. On average, the firms of the sample had an experience of 33.773 months using Facebook. The final ingredient used to assess Facebook capability was the firm's update activity that refers to the firm's activity in updating content on its Facebook site. The logic of this measure is that companies will have a high Facebook capability when they often update their site. We measured the updates by scoring with 1: Low or 5: High degree of content updating in this platform, considering when the firm had made the last comment on Facebook: 1: More than one month ago, 2: In the last month, 3: Two weeks ago, 4: In the last week, or 5: In the last two days (Benitez et al., 2018a). On average, the firms of the sample had an update activity of 2.740.

Twitter capability: It was also operationalized as a composite first-order construct with three indicators: spent time writing tweets,⁵ experience, and updates using information collected from the firm's site in Twitter and Twopcharts database. 71% of the firms of the sample had a Twitter site. Where a firm did not have a Twitter site, each of the specific ingredients of Twitter capability was coded as 0. The spent time writing tweets refers to the average hours that the firm had spent writing tweets from the creation of the Twitter firm's site until 2014. This ingredient is a good ingredient of Twitter capability. It is expected that a company learns to use and leverage Twitter through the investment of time in experimenting with Twitter functionalities. On average, the firms of the sample had invested 17.280 hours on Twitter. Experience and updates were measured in the same way as for Facebook capability (Braojos et al., 2019). On average, the firms of the sample had an experience of 35.752 months using Twitter and an update activity of 2.750.

⁵ The events were a specific feature of Facebook, which precluded us to use the number of events to evaluate Twitter capability or blog capability. We measured Twitter capability and blog capability based on the validated measurement scheme of Benitez et al. (2018a) and Benitez et al. (2020a) that include the spent time of the firm in writing tweets as an ingredient of Twitter capability, with information collected from the Twopcharts database. The time spent by the firm writing posts in Facebook and corporate blogs are not available in the Twopcharts database, which only provided information on Twitter company's sites.

Blog capability: Following the measurement scheme validated by Benitez et al. (2018a) and Benitez et al. (2020a), blog capability was measured through a construct composed by the experience and updates of the firm on the blog(s) using data collected from the firm's blog(s). We accessed the firm's blog by using the website of the company that provides a direct link to the corporate blog used by firms to interact with their customers and other stakeholders. 35% of the firms of the sample had a corporate blog. Where a firm did not have a corporate blog, each of the specific ingredients of blog capability was coded as 0. Experience and updates were measured in the same way as for Facebook capability. On average, the firms of the sample had an experience of 17.266 months using their corporate blog, and an update activity of 1.255.

3.2.3. Knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation

Knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation are composite first-order constructs composed of five indicators. We use one indicator for each year from 2014 to 2018 as follows. To measure each indicator of knowledge exploration and exploitation, we performed a structured content analysis following Joshi et al. (2010)'s measurement scheme, which has been widely accepted in the IS community.⁶ We use secondary data based on a comprehensive examination of corporate news from various data sources. These objective data are not susceptible to common method variance or respondents' perception (Joshi et al., 2010). In addition to Joshi et al. (2010), other prior IS studies have suggested these objective data and this measurement scheme as a feasible approach to measure IT applications that bolster knowledge management capabilities (e.g., Bharadwaj et al., 1999; Brynjolfsson and Hitt, 1996; Hitt and Brynjolfsson, 1996).

We measured knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation as follows. First, we used nine keywords related to IT applications that support knowledge exploration activities and nine keywords related to IT applications that support knowledge exploitation activities to choose the firm's news published in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018 from LexisNexis and Knowledge

⁶ As a reference, the Joshi et al.'s (2010) *Information Systems Research* paper has been cited 346 times in Google Scholar.

Management World databases.⁷ The selection of the IT applications that enable knowledge exploration and the list of IT applications that facilitate knowledge exploitation comes from the well-known study of Joshi et al. (2010). They “reviewed more than 300 articles and identified a list of IT application titles that were specifically mentioned and tied to one or more knowledge activities and capabilities in these articles.” (Joshi et al., 2010, p. 482). They “created a mapping between IT technologies and knowledge capabilities based on the technology capability linkages provided in the literature.” (Joshi et al., 2010, p. 482). They developed six iterations until they agreed on the list of IT applications that support knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. They also engaged two external experts in IT and knowledge management “to independently assess” their coding protocol and mapping between technology categories and knowledge capabilities.” (Joshi et al., 2010, p. 484).

The news coding protocol: We followed the news coding protocol established in well-known prior studies (Andrade and Kathuria, 2014; Chi et al., 2010; Joshi et al., 2010; Zelner et al., 2009). In our study, the news coding protocol was done by two authors and one independent external coder. Once they selected news containing these 18 keywords all these news were carefully read to decide whether the firm used (or not) the specific IT applications, making a distinction between those that supported the acquisition and storage of knowledge in the firm (knowledge exploration), and those that supported the application and usage of knowledge in the firm (knowledge exploitation). The irrelevant news was removed. The coders fully read the entire paragraph where a keyword appeared. The disagreements between the three coders were discussed until an agreement was reached. The coding protocol was then further refined based on the discussions. As an illustrative example, in one news, the coders found the following information: “The firm has migrated to a unified ERP backbone (with an expansion from nine to 12 instances)”. This piece of

⁷ In measuring knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, we focused on the news published in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018 to smooth out if the firm has good or bad year (Benitez et al., 2018a; Tanriverdi, 2005). We lagged the measures of knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation because we expected a lagged effect of social media capability on the exploration and exploitation of knowledge.

news shows that this firm uses an enterprise resource planning (ERP). As ERP is an IT application that supports knowledge exploration activities, we coded that this firm pursues knowledge exploration activities. In that way, knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation were measured as the total number of news on processes of knowledge management (knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation) enabled by IT applications in each year (Joshi et al., 2010). From the total number of news identified from the databases, in 10,099 news firms were found to use specific IT applications that support knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. The coders found and read 5291 news about knowledge exploration (538 news for 2014, 656 news for 2015, 954 news for 2016, 1044 news for 2017 and 2099 news for 2018), and for knowledge exploitation, they found and read 4808 news (341 news for 2014, 353 news for 2015, 796 news for 2016, 1438 news for 2017 and 1880 news for 2018). Table 2 provides a list of these 18 keywords.

Table 2: List of IT applications that enable knowledge exploration and exploitation

Construct	Reference	Keywords	Number of news found and read in the databases
Knowledge exploration	Joshi et al. (2010)	Enterprise resource planning system (ERP) Customer relationship management system (CRM) Supply chain management system (SCM) Database Content management system Repository Information retrieval Search software Data reading system	5291 news
Knowledge exploitation	Joshi et al. (2010)	Analytical software Business intelligence Data analytics Data mining Simulation software Decision support system Digital dashboard Online analytical processing Visualization	4808 news

3.2.4. Business analytics talent

Business analytics talent is a first-order construct composed of five indicators. To measure business analytics talent, we performed a structured content analysis on the firm's news published in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018 included in the LexisNexis database.⁸ Business analytics talent was measured as the total number of news on business analytics talent's features (i.e., distinctive attributes of business analytics talent) that were present in the firm. The data collection and coding protocol were developed as follows. First, based on the Ransbotham et al.'s (2015) applied research report, we selected a list of critical keywords related to business analytics talent. We identified on this report all the keywords related to the business analytics talent concept, resulting in a list of 22 critical keywords. Second, using these 22 keywords related to business analytics talent, we searched for the firm's news published in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018 included in the LexisNexis database. The news coding protocol used for business analytics talent is the same as the one used to assess knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. The paragraphs of the news where one of these keywords was identified were carefully read by the coders to decide whether the firm had, used, or applied the specific feature of business analytics talent. If the firm had, used, or applied the specific feature of business analytics talent mentioned in the news, then the coders counted one per each news, resulting in the total number of news containing these specific business analytics talent features. When one news included more than one keyword was counted as one. From the total number of news identified from the database, 1317 news (145 news for 2014, 170 news for 2015, 489 news for 2016, 223 news for 2017, and 290 news for 2018) were found to have, use, or apply the specific feature of business analytics. Table 3 provides a list of these 22 keywords.

⁸ We focused on the news published in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018 to smooth out if the firm has good or bad year (Benitez et al., 2018a; Tanriverdi, 2005). We lagged the measures of business analytics talent as we expected the moderating role of business analytics talent to be lagged over the time.

The data and measures of the key constructs included in the proposed research model include a good and objective proxy of these constructs and align well with the conceptualization of social media capability, knowledge exploration, knowledge exploitation, and business analytics talent. Table 4 provides a summary of the alignment between the conceptualization and the measures of the key constructs of this study.

3.2.5. Control variables

We controlled for firm size, industry, and firm age on knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. It is rational to expect that larger and more experienced firms may have more resources to invest in knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation firm's activities (Benitez and Walczuch, 2012). Firm size was measured as the natural logarithm of the average number of employees per firm, with data collected from Forbes database (Benitez et al., 2018a). Firm age was measured as the natural logarithm of the number of years operating of each firm (Chen et al., 2015), with information collected from Forbes database. The exploration and exploitation of knowledge may be dependent on the industry where the firm operates (Benitez et al., 2018a). The industry was measured as a dummy variable (0: Manufacturing firm, 1: Service firm) with information collected from Forbes database and the firm's website (Benitez et al., 2018a). Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics of the control variables.

Table 3: List of business analytics talent's key features

Construct	Reference	Keywords	Number of news found and read in the database
Business analytics talent	Ransbotham et al. (2015)	Analytics skill(s) / analytical skill(s) Analytics technology / analytical technology Analytics insights / analytical insights Analytics talent / analytical talent Analytics training / analytical training Analytics worker(s) / analytical worker(s) / analytics Employee(s) / analytical employee(s) Analytics capability(s) / analytical capability(ies) Analytics tool(s) / analytical tool(s) Analytics expertise / analytical expertise Analytics resource(s) / analytical resource(s) Descriptive analytics Predictive analytics Prescriptive analytics Data worker(s) / data employee(s) Data engineer(s) Data science Data manager(s) Data skill(s) Data scientist(s) Talent strategy(s) Big data capability(s) Chief Analytics Officer / Chief Data Officer	1317 news

4. Empirical analysis and results

The proposed research model was empirically tested using a PLS path modeling estimation. PLS is a well-developed, and full-fledged structural equation modeling (SEM) method of estimation (Henseler et al., 2016), which has been largely used in the field of IS (Benitez et al., 2020b; Chen et al., 2015; Ringle et al., 2012; Schmiedel et al., 2014), and its use is appropriate to test the proposed research model for several reasons. First, PLS is appropriate for confirmatory, and explanatory IS research (Benitez et al., 2020b; Henseler, 2018). Second, all constructs of the proposed model were specified as artifacts, and PLS is an optimal method of estimation for composite models (Benitez et al., 2020b; Henseler et al., 2014; Henseler et al., 2016). Third, the proposed model has a multidimensional construct (social media capability), which increases the complexity of the model. PLS method is considered more flexible than a covariance-based method of estimations to estimate this type of model (Hair et al., 2012).

Table 4: Construct conceptualization and measures

Construct	Conceptualization	Measure	Source
Social media capability	Firm's ability to purposely use and leverage external social media platforms to execute business activities	Second-order construct composed by Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability	Firm's Facebook, Twitter sites, Twopcharts database, and the corporate blog
Facebook capability	Firm's ability to use and leverage Facebook to execute business activities	Construct composed of number of events, experience, and updates	Firm's Facebook site
Twitter capability	Firm's ability to use and leverage Twitter to execute business activities	Construct composed of time spent posting tweets, experience, and updates	Firm's Twitter site and Twopcharts database
Blog capability	Firm's ability to use and leverage a blog to execute business activities	Construct composed of experience and updates	Corporate blog
Knowledge exploration	Learning process of experimenting with new knowledge and business opportunities by acquiring/creating, sharing, and storing this new knowledge	Total number of news on processes of knowledge exploration enabled by IT applications	LexisNexis database
Knowledge exploitation	Learning process of assimilating, reusing, reinterpreting, applying, and leveraging existing/new knowledge	Total number of news on processes of knowledge exploitation enabled by IT applications	LexisNexis database
Business analytics talent	Firm's resource that refers to the talent of people on performing business analytics to be able to transform data in insights valuable for supporting business activities	Natural logarithm of the total number of news on business analytics talent's features about the firm	LexisNexis database

Table 5: Descriptive statistics of control variables

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation
Firm size	2335.187	5997.762
Industry	0.480	0.502
Firm age	34.740	21.353

ADANCO software package: We employed the statistical software package Advanced Analysis for Composites (ADANCO) 2.1 Professional for Windows (<http://www.composite-modeling.com/>) (Henseler and Dijkstra, 2015). ADANCO is a software package for composite-based SEM with a clear graphical user interface. It facilitates various second-generation statistical analyses, such as confirmatory factor analysis, confirmatory composite analysis, and SEM. Its version 1.0 was introduced in 2015 by Joerg Henseler and Theo Dijkstra (Henseler and Dijkstra, 2015) to implement their recent developments, i.e., consistent PLS (Dijkstra and Henseler, 2015a,

2015b), the HTMT (Henseler et al., 2015), and the confirmatory composite analysis (Henseler et al., 2014). “ADANCO was programmed as a response to the criticism of existing PLS software (expressed, for instance, by Ronkko and Evermann, 2013). Two of ADANCO’s features are particularly worth mentioning: In contrast to older PLS software such as PLS-Graph and SmartPLS, the specified graphical model corresponds with the estimated statistical model. Consequently, ADANCO provides consistent estimates for the statistical model at hand. And whereas other PLS software (e.g., PLS-Graph, SmartPLS, WarpPLS, or XLSTAT-PLS) mainly aims at exploratory and predictive research, ADANCO is fully devoted to confirmatory research. As such, it puts goodness of model fit central; it encourages analysts to make use of bootstrap-based tests of goodness of model fit. Besides, it can consistently estimate both composite and common factor models. ADANCO is maintained regularly; version 2.2 will be launched in Fall 2020. Moreover, a dedicated textbook will be published at the end of 2020 (Henseler, 2020).”⁹ We use the ADANCO software package because it provides consistent estimates, and it is appropriate for confirmatory research, as our study.

4.1. Measurement model evaluation

4.1.1. Confirmatory composite analysis

We conducted a confirmatory composite analysis to check if our structure of composite measures was correct and supported by the data (Benitez et al., 2020b; Henseler et al., 2014). This confirmatory composite analysis analyzes the adequacy of the composite model, comparing the empirical correlation matrix and the model-implied correlation matrix. It shows whether the structure of the measurements (the saturated model) is correct. We evaluated the discrepancy between the empirical correlation matrix and the saturated model-implied correlation matrix at first, second-order, and control variable levels (Benitez et al., 2020b; Henseler, 2015) by calculating

⁹ This statement comes from two interviews conducted by the second author of the current manuscript to Professor Joerg Henseler (University of Twente, The Netherlands) on May 2 and May 25, 2020. We want to thank Professor Henseler his encouragement, help, availability, and support for the completion of these interviews and the execution of this paper.

the standardized root mean squared residual (SRMR), unweighted least squares (ULS) discrepancy (d_{ULS}), and geodesic discrepancy (d_G) (Henseler et al., 2014), three well-accepted measures of the discrepancy mentioned above (Benitez et al., 2020b; Kim et al., 2019). The structure of measurements is supported by the confirmatory composite analysis when the value of the discrepancies is lower than the 95% (or 99%) quantile of the bootstrap discrepancies. When the value of the discrepancies is lower than the 95%-quantile of the bootstrap discrepancies, the structure of measurements is supported with a 5% probability (Benitez et al., 2018b). When the value of the discrepancies is lower than the 99%-quantile of the bootstrap discrepancies, the structure of measurements is supported with a 1% probability (Benitez et al., 2020b). All discrepancies are below the 95%-quantile of the bootstrap discrepancies (Henseler et al., 2016) for both first and second-order steps. None of these two models should be rejected based on an alpha level of 0.05. This means that with a probability of 5%, we can claim that the structure of measures of our model is correct. Table 6 shows the overall model fit evaluation for the confirmatory composite analysis.

Table 6: Confirmatory composite analysis (saturated model¹⁰)

Discrepancy	First-order level			Second-order level		
	Value	HI ₉₅	Conclusion	Value	HI ₉₅	Conclusion
SRMR	0.084	0.112	Supported	0.065	0.093	Supported
d_{ULS}	2.446	4.418	Supported	0.042	0.087	Supported
d_G	4.437	19.535	Supported	0.008	0.026	Supported

4.1.2. Evaluation of the measurement properties

The constructs of our model (social media capability, knowledge exploration, knowledge exploitation, business analytics talent) are composite. Thus we evaluated their multicollinearity, weights, loadings, and level of significance (Benitez et al., 2020b; Cenfetelli and Bassellier, 2009), by running a 4,999 subsamples bootstrap analysis. To ensure multicollinearity is not a problem,

¹⁰ “The saturated model corresponds to a model in which all constructs can freely correlate. It is related to the measurement model (Benitez et al., 2020b). The saturated model is useful to assess the quality of the measurement model, because potential model misfit can be entirely attributed to measurement model misspecification” (Henseler, 2017, p.183).

the variance inflation factor (VIF) must be below the suggested threshold of 10 (Benitez et al., 2020b; Tanriverdi and Uysal, 2015). For weights estimated by Mode A, an assessment of multicollinearity is not necessary as they equal scaled covariances and therefore ignore multicollinearity (Benitez et al., 2020b; Rigdon, 2012). Then, high VIFs for knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation (both constructs estimated by Mode A) are not a problem in the proposed model. The VIFs of the indicators/dimensions of the proposed model which are estimated by Sum Score range from 1.000 to 1.470, suggesting that multicollinearity is not a problem in our data (Benitez et al., 2018b). All indicators/dimensions of the model have significant weights (ranging from 0.133^{***} to 0.714^{***} for indicators, and from 0.483^{***} to 0.483^{***} for dimensions) and significant loadings (ranging from 0.508^{***} to 0.979^{***} for indicators, and from 0.520^{***} to 0.780^{***} for dimensions). We performed the two-step approach to estimate the proposed model since social media capability is a second-order construct. First, we freely correlated all the first-order constructs and dimensions of the second-order constructs to obtain the latent variables scores of the dimensions. Second, we used these latent variables scores as the ingredients that compose social media capability.

We executed the following weighting scheme in our estimation. First, we started the estimation by using Mode B for all constructs. Second, for those constructs with VIFs values higher than 10 and/or negative weights, we employed Mode A (Benitez et al., 2018b). Finally, Sum Score was selected as the preferred weighting scheme of some of the constructs, as suggested by the incremental improvements in the overall fit of the estimated model (Benitez et al., 2020b). The measurement model evaluation is presented in Table 7. The results in the confirmatory composite analysis and the evaluation of the measurement properties are good and enable us to proceed with testing the proposed hypotheses included in the proposed research model.

4.2. Structural model assessment

4.2.1. Overall model fit evaluation of the estimated model

The overall goodness of the estimated model fit was also evaluated in a similar way to the confirmatory composite analysis, but for the estimated model(s) (Dijkstra and Henseler, 2015a; Henseler et al., 2014). This measure of goodness of fit evaluates the discrepancy between the empirical correlation matrix and the estimated model-implied correlation matrix (Benitez et al., 2018b; Henseler et al., 2014; Henseler, 2015). The lower the SRMR, d_{ULS} , and d_G , the better the fit between the proposed model and the data (Henseler and Dijkstra, 2015). Overall, our proposed model should not be rejected based on the alpha level of 0.05 because all the discrepancies are below the 95%-quantile of the bootstrap discrepancies (Benitez et al., 2020b; Henseler et al., 2014). These results mean that with a probability of 5%, we can claim that the proposed research model of social media and knowledge exploration and exploitation is correct to explain how the corporate and IT world functions.

Table 7: Measurement properties evaluation at first- and second-order level

Construct/indicator ¹¹	Mean	S.D.	VIF	Weight	Loading
Social media capability (Sum Score)					
Facebook capability: Facebook activity of the firm in terms of (Sum Score)			1.470	0.483***	0.770***
Number of events	5.510	18.549	1.087	0.539***	0.703***
Experience	33.773	25.582	1.010	0.539***	0.508***
Updates	2.740	2.223	1.094	0.539***	0.644***
Twitter capability: Twitter activity of the firm in terms of: (Mode A)			1.473	0.483***	0.780***
Spent time	17.280	32.149	1.307	0.262***	0.669***
Experience	35.752	27.651	2.114	0.431***	0.887***
Updates	2.750	2.284	2.254	0.483***	0.917***
Blog capability: Blog activity of the firm in terms of: (Sum Score)			1.002	0.483***	0.520***
Experience	17.266	31.681	1.000	0.714***	0.701***

¹¹ The dominant indicator approach can be executed in the ADANCO software package and refers to the indicator of a construct that is expected to correlate with the construct positively. It represents the most important ingredient of the composite construct when this information is known or assumed theoretically before the estimation (Benitez et al., 2020b). None of the constructs/indicators was considered as the dominant in our PLS estimation because we preferred to let the data and the analysis to dictate the weights of the ingredients for each construct freely.

Updates	1.255	1.949	1.000	0.714***	0.701***
Knowledge exploration: Number of news on processes of knowledge exploration enabled by IT applications (Mode A)					
Knowledge exploration 2014			6.623	0.255***	0.864***
Knowledge exploration 2015			3.282	0.207***	0.857***
Knowledge exploration 2016			3.541	0.235***	0.861***
Knowledge exploration 2017			14.038	0.279***	0.963***
Knowledge exploration 2018			1.564	0.206***	0.639***
Knowledge exploitation: Number of news on processes of knowledge exploitation enabled by IT applications (Mode A)					
Knowledge exploitation 2014			5.117	0.326***	0.920***
Knowledge exploitation 2015			13.243	0.286***	0.979***
Knowledge exploitation 2016			149.310	0.164*	0.960***
Knowledge exploitation 2017			191.406	0.133***	0.950***
Knowledge exploitation 2018			101.372	0.144***	0.949***
Business analytics talent: Number of news on analytics talent's per firm (Mode A)					
Business analytics talent 2014			1.874	0.201***	0.763***
Business analytics talent 2015			9.504	0.244***	0.947***
Business analytics talent 2016			2.950	0.234***	0.829***
Business analytics talent 2017			5.411	0.261***	0.885***
Business analytics talent 2018			1.620	0.251***	0.758***
Firm size: Natural logarithm of the total number of full-time employees					
Industry: The primary industry of the firm (0: Manufacturing industry, 1: Service industry)					
Firm age: Natural logarithm of the number of years operating the firm					

4.2.2. Test of hypotheses

To test the hypothesized relationships, we performed a PLS estimation (Dijkstra and Henseler, 2015b) by evaluating the beta coefficients and its significance of the proposed model running a bootstrap analysis with 4,999 subsamples. The R^2 values and the effect size (f^2) of the proposed relationships were also evaluated. First, we evaluated a baseline model to test H1 and H2. This baseline model describes the base relationships, including all control variables, and excluding the moderator variable (business analytics talent). Second, we tested model 1, which includes business analytics talent and adds the interaction terms (social media capability * Business

analytics talent) to the baseline model to test H3. H1 and H2 are supported, suggesting that social media capability enables knowledge exploration (H1) ($\beta = 0.270$, $p_{\text{one-tailed}} < 0.001$), and knowledge exploitation (H2) ($\beta = 0.134$, $p_{\text{one-tailed}} < 0.01$). H3 is also supported, which suggests that the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration is amplified (positively moderated and reinforced) when the firm has business analytics talent ($\beta = 0.584$, $p_{\text{one-tailed}} < 0.01$). Thus, business analytics talent plays a reinforcing moderator role in this relationship. Control variables did not show any significant relationship with knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation in the context of our model, except industry. The relationships between industry and knowledge exploration and industry and knowledge exploitation are positive and significant, which suggests that firms of services industries explore and exploit knowledge more than firms of manufacturing industries. The R^2 values are 0.177 and 0.060 for the baseline model, and 0.750 and 0.060 for model 1. The f^2 values of the key relationships of the proposed model range from 0.079 to 0.017 for the baseline model, and from 0.017 to 0.136 for model 1, which indicate from weak to medium-large effect sizes between the exogenous and endogenous variables of the proposed theory (Benitez et al., 2020b; Cohen, 1988). Figure 2 depicts the results of the empirical analysis. Table 8 shows the results of the test of hypotheses. Table 9 presents the correlation matrix.

Table 8: Results of the test of hypotheses

Beta coefficient	Baseline model	Model 1
Social media capability → Knowledge exploration (H1)	0.270*** (4.345) [0.173, 0.396]	0.204* (1.953) [0.065, 0.455]
Social media capability → Knowledge exploitation (H2)	0.134** (2.334) [0.070, 0.313]	0.134** (2.334) [0.070, 0.313]
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration (H3)		0.584** (2.678) [0.196, 0.916]
Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration		0.209 (0.911) [-0.206, 0.562]
Firm size → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.034 (0.520) [-0.100, 0.159]	-0.042 (-0.883) [-0.160, 0.029]
Firm size → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.054	0.054

	(0.717) [-0.039, 0.260]	(0.717) [-0.039, 0.260]		
Industry → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.224*** (4.158) [0.126, 0.341]	0.102* (1.868) [0.004, 0.219]		
Industry → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.153*** (3.610) [0.099, 0.264]	0.153*** (3.610) [0.099, 0.264]		
Firm age → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	-0.058 (-0.863) [-0.185, 0.070]	-0.025 (-0.620) [-0.090, 0.071]		
Firm age → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.055 (0.493) [-0.205, 0.194]	0.055 (0.477) [-0.205, 0.194]		
Endogenous variables	R²	Adjusted R²	R²	Adjusted R²
Knowledge exploration	0.177	0.142	0.750	0.734
Knowledge exploitation	0.060	0.021	0.060	0.021
Discrepancy	Value	HI₉₅	Value	HI₉₅
SRMR	0.027	0.099	0.045	0.143
d_{ULs}	0.026	0.356	0.160	1.586
d_G	0.008	0.288	0.593	6.253
f²				
Social media capability → Knowledge exploration (H1)	0.079		0.105	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploitation (H2)	0.017		0.017	
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration (H3)			0.136	
Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration			0.016	
Firm size → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.001		0.006	
Firm size → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.003		0.003	
Industry → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.049		0.032	
Industry → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.020		0.020	
Firm age → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.003		0.002	
Firm age → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.003		0.003	

Note: t-values in parentheses. Bootstrapping 95% confidence interval bias corrected in square bracket (based on n = 4999 subsamples). †p < 0.10, *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 [based on t(4,998), one-tailed test].

Figure 2: Results of the empirical analysis

Table 9: Correlation matrix

	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Social media capability	1.000									
1.1. Facebook capability	0.770	1.000								
1.2. Twitter capability	0.780	0.566	1.000							
1.3. Blog capability	0.520	0.028	0.049	1.000						
2. Knowledge exploration	0.289	0.303	0.311	-0.017	1.000					
3. Knowledge exploitation	0.152	0.088	0.203	0.024	0.152	1.000				
4. Business analytics talent	0.257	0.250	0.278	0.004	0.835	0.280	1.000			
5. Firm size	0.067	0.054	0.074	0.011	0.103	0.123	0.177	1.000		
6. Industry	0.207	0.273	0.229	-0.074	0.319	0.198	0.296	0.292	1.000	
7. Firm age	-0.147	-0.196	-0.178	0.069	-0.140	0.018	-0.086	-0.156	0.278	1.000

4.3. Test of robustness

We tested for the robustness of the proposed research model by estimating eight alternative/competing models. In the first alternative model, social media capability affects knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, and business analytics talent moderates both the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration, and the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploitation. The rationale for this model is that

firms may additionally use analytical skills to assimilate and exploit knowledge (e.g., making predictions). In the second alternative model, social media capability affects knowledge ambidexterity (i.e., a composite first-order construct composed by two indicators: knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation), and business analytics talent moderates the relationship between social media capability and knowledge ambidexterity. The rationale for this research model is to examine the effects of social media and business analytics talent in the simultaneous pursuing of exploration and exploitation (i.e., knowledge ambidexterity). In the third alternative model, social media capability affects knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, which in turn affect firm performance, keeping the moderating role of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration. The rationale for this research model is to examine the final and full effects on firm performance. In the fourth alternative model, social media capability enables knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, and knowledge exploration facilitates knowledge exploitation, preserving the moderating role of business analytics talent. Benitez et al. (2018d) found that firms explore business opportunities first and then they exploit opportunities through operational capabilities (the heart and core of the company). Drawn on Benitez et al. (2018d), the rationale for this fourth alternative research model is that knowledge exploration may precede knowledge exploitation. In the fifth alternative model, social media capability enables knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, knowledge exploration facilitates knowledge exploitation, and business analytics talent moderates both the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration and the relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation.

In the sixth alternative model, we measure Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability with experience and updates, that is, with homogeneous measurements, but every other model specification keeps the same. The seventh alternative model controls for advertising spending on knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. The rationale is that the development of social media capability and its effects on knowledge exploration and knowledge

exploitation may be affected by the marketing activities of the firm. Finally, the eighth alternative model combines the model specifications of the second and seventh alternative models but estimating knowledge ambidexterity multiplying knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. The next section presents the results of the estimation of these eighth alternative models.

4.3.1. The moderator role of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploitation

In the first alternative model, we assumed that social media capability affects knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, and business analytics talent moderates both relationships (i.e., social media capability affects knowledge exploration, and social media capability affects knowledge exploitation). The rationale to test this model is that business analytics talent may enable firms to extract, monitor, and analyze unstructured existing/new knowledge to be reused, transformed, applied, and leveraged into the firm, which may reinforce the effect of social media capability on knowledge exploitation. This first alternative model yielded results similar to those obtained in the proposed model, but the moderating effect of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploitation was not significant ($\beta = -0.476$). Table 10 shows the results of this robustness model. Thus, business analytics talent does not amplify the effect of social media capability on knowledge exploitation.

Table 10: Results of the test of robustness about the moderator role of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploitation

Beta coefficient	Baseline model		Model 1	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploration (H1)	0.270*** (4.345) [0.173, 0.396]		0.240* (1.926) [0.021, 0.508]	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploitation (H2)	0.134** (2.334) [0.070, 0.313]		-0.025 (-0.163) [-0.247, 0.394]	
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration (H3a)			0.673* (1.897) [-0.601, 0.952]	
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploitation (H3b)			-0.476 (-0.670) [-1.411, 1.438]	
Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration			0.111 (0.292) [-0.288, 1.116]	
Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploitation			0.708 (1.070) [-0.901, 1.881]	
Firm size → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.034 (0.520) [-0.100, 0.159]		-0.040 (-0.849) [-0.160, 0.028]	
Firm size → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.054 (0.717) [-0.039, 0.260]		0.016 (0.262) [-0.088, 0.167]	
Industry → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.224*** (4.158) [0.126, 0.341]		0.101* (1.813) [-0.004, 0.216]	
Industry → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.153*** (3.610) [0.099, 0.264]		0.089† (1.542) [-0.046, 0.191]	
Firm age → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	-0.058 (-0.863) [-0.185, 0.070]		-0.023 (-0.552) [-0.092, 0.073]	
Firm age → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.055 (-0.863) [-0.205, 0.194]		0.061 (0.632) [-0.142, 0.207]	
Endogenous variables	R²	Adjusted R²	R²	Adjusted R²
Knowledge exploration	0.177	0.142	0.750	0.734
Knowledge exploitation	0.060	0.021	0.120	0.063
Discrepancy	Value	HI₉₅	Value	HI₉₅
SRMR	0.027	0.099	0.037	0.122
d_{ULS}	0.026	0.356	0.108	1.151
d_G	0.008	0.288	0.455	6.266

4.3.2. The relationship between social media capability and knowledge ambidexterity

In the second alternative model, we propose that social media capability affects knowledge ambidexterity, and business analytics talent moderates the relationship between social media capability and knowledge ambidexterity. Thus, we examine the potential enabling role of social media capability on knowledge ambidexterity and the potential amplifying role of business analytics talent in this relationship. We operationalized knowledge ambidexterity as a composite first-order construct composed of two indicators: knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. Results show that the link between social media capability and knowledge ambidexterity in the baseline model (i.e., a model describing the base relationship between social media capability and knowledge ambidexterity, including all control variables and excluding business analytics talent) was positive and significant ($\beta = 0.285$, $p_{\text{one-tailed}} < 0.001$). Moreover, the moderating effect of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge ambidexterity was also positive and significant ($\beta = 0.524$, $p_{\text{one-tailed}} < 0.05$). The results of this empirical analysis suggest that firms effectively using social media simultaneously explore and exploit knowledge, and business analytics talent amplify the impact of social media capability on knowledge ambidexterity. Table 11 presents the results of this alternative model.

4.3.3. The relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation and firm performance

In the third alternative model, we propose that social media capability affects knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, which in turn affects firm performance, preserving the moderating role of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration. Prior research has suggested a firm's knowledge management activities as a source of superior firm performance (Lee et al., 2020; Tanriverdi, 2005). The ability to bring new knowledge from social media to the firm (i.e., knowledge exploration) increases the diversity and heterogeneity of the firm's knowledge pool, and the possibilities of new knowledge combinations, thus improving firm performance such as innovation performance (Katila and Ahuja,

2002). When the discovered knowledge is exploited and leveraged, the firm creates business value (e.g., converting new knowledge in product and process innovation) (Benitez et al., 2018b; Benitez et al., 2018d, Lubatkin et al., 2006). In this alternative model, we operationalized firm performance in terms of financial performance, marketing performance, and innovation performance of the firm. To measure financial performance and marketing performance, we collected data from the Datastream database from 2014 to 2018. To measure innovation performance, we collected data from the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office in the same period. The links between knowledge exploration and firm performance ($\beta = 0.145$, $p_{\text{one-tailed}} < 0.05$), and knowledge exploitation and firm performance ($\beta = 0.256$, $p_{\text{one-tailed}} < 0.001$) are positive and significant. Therefore, the results of the empirical analysis for this alternative model suggest that firms effectively using social media to explore and exploit knowledge, and the firm's proficiency in exploring new knowledge, and exploiting existing/new knowledge enable to improve firm performance. As the analysis of the effects of knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation on firm performance goes beyond the goal of this paper and it has already explored in prior IS research (e.g., Kathuria et al. 2016), we have kept this model only in the robustness check. Table 12 shows the results of this alternative model.

Table 11: Results of the test of robustness on the relationship between social media capability and knowledge ambidexterity

Beta coefficient	Baseline model		Model 1	
Social media capability → Knowledge ambidexterity	0.285*** (4.439) [0.184, 0.420]		0.212* (2.114) [0.045, 0.045]	
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge ambidexterity			0.524* (2.022) [-0.026, 0.845]	
Business analytics talent → Knowledge ambidexterity			0.270 (0.949) [-0.113, 0.890]	
Firm size → Knowledge ambidexterity (control variable)	0.050 (0.654) [-0.088, 0.217]		-0.036 (-0.788) [-0.144, 0.037]	
Industry → Knowledge ambidexterity (control variable)	0.252*** (4.507) [0.146, 0.366]		0.112* (2.014) [-0.025, 0.203]	
Firm age → Knowledge ambidexterity (control variable)	-0.030 (-0.396) [-0.185, 0.112]		-0.011 (-0.269) [-0.069, 0.101]	
Endogenous variables	R²	Adjusted R²	R²	Adjusted R²
Knowledge ambidexterity	0.204	0.170	0.765	0.750
Discrepancy	Value	HI₉₅	Value	HI₉₅
SRMR	0.031	0.089	0.043	0.126
d_{ULS}	0.033	0.282	0.142	1.229
d_G	0.009	0.100	0.493	6.174

Table 12: Results of the test of robustness on the effect of knowledge exploration and exploitation on firm performance

Beta coefficient	Baseline model		Model 1	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploration (H1)	0.270*** (4.343) [0.173, 0.396]		0.204* (1.957) [0.065, 0.457]	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploitation (H2)	0.133** (2.323) [0.070, 0.315]		0.133** (2.323) [0.070, 0.315]	
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration (H3)			0.584** (2.684) [0.194, 0.914]	
Knowledge exploration → Firm performance	0.145* (1.860) [-0.010, 0.284]		0.145* (1.860) [-0.010, 0.284]	
Knowledge exploitation → Firm performance	0.266*** (2.548) [0.039, 0.466]		0.256*** (2.548) [0.039, 0.466]	
Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration			0.207 (0.905) [-0.206, 0.561]	
Firm size → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.034 (0.512) [-0.101, 0.159]		-0.043 (-0.888) [-0.160, 0.028]	

Firm size → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.053 (0.701) [-0.039, 0.262]	0.053 (0.701) [-0.039, 0.262]		
Firm size → Firm performance (control variable)	0.332** (3.585) [0.149, 0.511]	0.332*** (3.585) [0.149, 0.511]		
Industry → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.224*** (4.158) [0.126, 0.341]	0.102* (1.871) [0.004, 0.219]		
Industry → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.152*** (3.577) [0.099, 0.265]	0.152*** (3.577) [0.099, 0.265]		
Firm age → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	-0.058 (-0.863) [-0.186, 0.070]	-0.025 (-0.620) [-0.090, 0.071]		
Firm age → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.056 (0.490) [-0.205, 0.195]	0.056 (0.490) [-0.205, 0.195]		
Industry → Firm performance (control variable)	-0.060 (-0.566) [-0.287, 0.130]	-0.060 (-0.566) [-0.287, 0.130]		
Firm age → Firm performance (control variable)	-0.133* (-1.611) [-0.286, 0.038]	-0.133* (-1.611) [-0.286, 0.038]		
Endogenous variables	R²	Adjusted R²	R²	Adjusted R²
Knowledge exploration	0.177	0.142	0.748	0.732
Knowledge exploitation	0.060	0.020	0.060	0.020
Firm performance	0.214	0.172	0.214	0.172
Discrepancy	Value	HI₉₅	Value	HI₉₅
SRMR	0.031	0.099	0.047	0.137
d_{ULS}	0.042	0.439	0.198	1.710
d_G	0.011	0.296	0.605	6.404

4.3.4. The relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation

In the fourth alternative model, we assume that social media capability affects knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, and knowledge exploration affects knowledge exploitation preserving the moderating role of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration. The theoretical argument to test this model bases on prior studies, which suggest that exploration enables exploitation in different contexts. Evidence has been shown about the effect of exploration on exploitation on the context of business opportunities (Benitez et al., 2018d) and the context of mergers and acquisitions (Benitez et al., 2018b). However, in the specific context of knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation in

our sample of U.S. small firms, we do not find a significant relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation ($\beta = 0.071$). Future research should explore the relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation in other geographic contexts and sizes of firms.

4.3.5. The moderator role of business analytics talent in the relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation

In the fifth alternative model, we assume that social media capability affects knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation, knowledge exploration affects knowledge exploitation, keeping the moderator role of business analytics talent in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration, and adding a moderator role of business analytics talent in the relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. The rationale to test this model is that business analytics talent can be the pivotal complementary resource to move the social media-enabled knowledge explored into exploited knowledge. This additional analysis might explain the lack of support for the effect of knowledge exploration on knowledge exploitation in the fourth alternative model.¹² However, in this alternative model, the moderating effect of business analytics talent in the relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation was not significant ($\beta = -0.413$). Future IS research should explore the relationship between knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation and the potential moderator role of business analytics talent on firms with different sizes (e.g., small European firms) and different geographic contexts (e.g., Asian companies).

¹² We very much appreciate the suggestion of one anonymous reviewer on this issue.

4.3.6. The model with homogeneous measurements for Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability

We are confident with the alignment between the conceptualization and the measurements of social media capability, and they have also been supported by the confirmatory composite analysis. However, there are small differences in the ingredients of Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability that are explained by the nature of the social media (e.g., number of events in Facebook capability), and the data availability (e.g., spent time writing tweets of Twitter capability). The two common and homogeneous measurements of the three social media capabilities are experience and updates. In the sixth alternative model, we measure Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability only with experience and updates, that is, with homogeneous measurements, but every other model specification keeps the same. Table 13 presents the results of this alternative model. The results of this model are consistent with our results of the test of hypotheses and indicate that the variation in the ingredients of Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability does not affect the findings of this study.

Table 13: Results of the test of robustness measuring Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability with experience and updates

Beta coefficient	Baseline model		Model 1	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploration (H1)	0.292*** (5.037) [0.190, 0.416]		0.298** (2.543) [0.024, 0.495]	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploitation (H2)	0.154* (1.928) [0.124, 0.436]		0.154* (1.928) [0.124, 0.436]	
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration (H3)			0.832** (2.268) [-0.150, 1.211]	
Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration			-0.077 (-0.208) [-0.528, 0.916]	
Firm size → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.113† (1.318) [-0.046, 0.294]		0.047 (0.687) [-0.090, 0.177]	
Firm size → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.033 (0.308) [-0.055, 0.356]		0.033 (0.308) [-0.055, 0.356]	
Industry → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.194*** (3.614) [0.111, 0.313]		0.092* (1.975) [0.001, 0.183]	
Industry → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.111* (1.953) [0.095, 0.304]		0.111* (1.953) [0.066, 0.284]	
Firm age → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	-0.073* (-1.188) [-0.190, 0.051]		-0.042 (-1.158) [-0.112, 0.033]	
Firm age → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.103 (0.955) [-0.162, 0.227]		0.103 (0.955) [-0.162, 0.227]	
Endogenous variables	R²	Adjusted R²	R²	Adjusted R²
Knowledge exploration	0.198	0.165	0.756	0.740
Knowledge exploitation	0.051	0.011	0.051	0.011
Discrepancy	Value	HI₉₅	Value	HI₉₅
SRMR	0.022	0.093	0.041	0.138
d_{ULS}	0.017	0.311	0.130	1.480
d_G	0.008	0.186	0.562	1.627

4.3.7. Model controlling for firm's advertising spending on knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation

The seventh alternative model controls for firm's advertising spending on knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. The rationale is that the development of social media capability and its effects on knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation may be affected by the firm's

marketing activities and resources. We measure the firm's advertising spending as the average annual advertising spending of the firm for the years 2014-2018 with information from the ORBIS database. Table 14 presents the results of this model, which suggest that after controlling for the firm's advertising spending, the findings of our study are consistent and robust.

4.3.8. Model controlling for firm's advertising spending on knowledge ambidexterity

The eighth alternative model combines the model specifications of the second and seventh alternative models but estimating knowledge ambidexterity multiplying knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. This ingredient specification is another alternative way to measure ambidexterity, as it has been suggested in prior organizational ambidexterity literature. The firm's advertising spending (control variable) was measured as in the seventh alternative model. Table 15 presents the results of the eighth alternative model. This additional analysis suggests that the construct specification of knowledge ambidexterity after to control for advertising spending does not affect the findings of this study.

Table 14: Results of the test of robustness for the model controlling for firm's advertising spending

Beta coefficient	Baseline model		Model 1	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploration (H1)	0.270*** (4.300) [0.170, 0.398]		0.204* (1.944) [0.065, 0.314]	
Social media capability → Knowledge exploitation (H2)	0.134** (2.300) [0.065, 0.314]		0.134** (2.300) [0.066, 0.314]	
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration (H3)			0.584** (2.666) [0.193, 0.918]	
Business analytics talent → Knowledge exploration			0.209 (0.908) [-0.205, 0.565]	
Firm size → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.033 (0.464) [-0.107, 0.168]		-0.042 (-0.817) [-0.170, 0.033]	
Firm size → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.054 (0.702) [-0.036, 0.274]		0.054 (0.702) [-0.036, 0.274]	
Industry → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	0.223*** (4.168) [0.128, 0.341]		0.102* (1.908) [0.007, 0.217]	
Industry → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.153*** (3.558) [0.076, 0.269]		0.153*** (3.558) [0.101, 0.269]	
Firm age → Knowledge exploration (control variable)	-0.058 (-0.862) [-0.186, 0.074]		-0.025 (-0.607) [-0.091, 0.073]	
Firm age → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.055 (0.470) [-0.205, 0.202]		0.055 (0.470) [-0.205, 0.202]	
Advertising spending → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	-0.010 (-0.226) [-0.053, 0.113]		0.001 (0.025) [-0.052, 0.052]	
Advertising spending → Knowledge exploitation (control variable)	0.001 (0.012) [-0.039, 0.143]		0.001 (0.048) [-0.039, 0.143]	
Endogenous variables	R²	Adjusted R²	R²	Adjusted R²
Knowledge exploration	0.177	0.133	0.750	0.731
Knowledge exploitation	0.060	0.010	0.060	0.010
Discrepancy	Value	HI₉₅	Value	HI₉₅
SRMR	0.025	0.170	0.042	0.138
d_{ULS}	0.028	0.515	0.163	1.738
d_G	0.009	0.700	0.595	6.399

Note: The results of the analysis of this table measures the firm's advertising spending as the average annual advertising spending for the years 2014-2018. We repeated the analysis by measuring advertising spending only for 2013, only for 2014, and estimating an average for the period 2013-2017. All the results of these alternative measures for the firm's advertising spending yield similar results.

Table 15: Results of the test of robustness for the model controlling for firm’s advertising spending on knowledge ambidexterity (estimated as multiplying knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation)

Beta coefficient	Baseline model with advertising spending		Model 1 with advertising spending	
	R ²	Adjusted R ²	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Social media capability → Knowledge ambidexterity	0.190* (1.896) [0.080, 0.445]		0.230* (2.196) [0.025, 0.457]	
Social media capability * Business analytics talent → Knowledge ambidexterity			0.397* (2.003) [0.052, 0.851]	
Business analytics talent → Knowledge ambidexterity			-0.022 (-0.099) [-0.266, 0.615]	
Firm size → Knowledge ambidexterity (control variable)	0.223† (1.483) [-0.069, 0.461]		0.188† (1.261) [-0.113, 0.392]	
Industry → Knowledge ambidexterity (control variable)	0.137* (2.065) [0.043, 0.298]		0.069 (1.198) [-0.043, 0.190]	
Firm age → Knowledge ambidexterity (control variable)	-0.032 (-0.489) [-0.153, 0.107]		-0.013 (-0.264) [-0.094, 0.109]	
Advertising spending → Knowledge ambidexterity (control variable)	0.191* (1.971) [0.088, 0.442]		0.014 (0.213) [-0.066, 0.192]	
Endogenous variables	R²	Adjusted R²	R²	Adjusted R²
Knowledge ambidexterity	0.141	0.095	0.278	0.223
Discrepancy	Value	HI₉₅	Value	HI₉₉
SRMR	0.017	0.082	0.089	0.209
d_{ULS}	0.011	0.239	0.616	3.396
d_G	0.007	0.481	1.421	1.824

5. Discussion and core conclusions

5.1. Summary of findings

Managing organizational knowledge is critical in increasingly competitive environments (He et al., 2015). Prior IS literature has considered social media as a key source of information and data (Leonardi, 2014). However, acquiring and generating social media data is not a sufficient condition to create business value. Monitoring, analyzing, and identifying relevant information is key in transforming social media data into valuable information and knowledge, and business gains (Ransbotham et al., 2015). Firms find difficulties in efficiently selecting and assimilating social media data and converting them into business benefits (Chan et al., 2016). We propose that firms

with social media capability can exploit and explore knowledge. Moreover, we argue that the effective application of social media data in business activities will be achieved if firms can explore and exploit knowledge, and they leverage business analytics talent. This study aimed to analyze the impact of social media capability on knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation and the potential moderator role of business analytics talent. The proposed research model was tested using a unique set of archival data on a sample of U.S. firms. After checking for eight additional alternative explanations/research models in a test of robustness, the empirical analysis provides strong support to our proposed research model.¹³

How do social media capability influence knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation? The results of the empirical analysis show that social media capability facilitates the firm to explore and exploit knowledge as social media are new organizational channels that facilitate knowledge management (e.g., acquiring and transferring new knowledge; and recombining, modifying, and integrating new/existing knowledge). Social media capability facilitates firms' acquisition of knowledge from customers, competitors, and suppliers. In this way, firms can identify valuable knowledge from suppliers, competitors, and customers, and apply and leverage this useful knowledge to achieve higher firm performance. Even though we find that social media capability enables both exploration and exploitation of knowledge, the effect is greater on knowledge exploration than on knowledge exploitation, which suggests that social media play a more important role in enabling exploration of new knowledge than the exploitation of existing knowledge. Besides, business analytics talent amplifies the impact of social media capability on knowledge exploration because it helps the firm to create meaningful new knowledge from unstructured new knowledge quickly. Dong and Yang (2020) find that social media diversity and

¹³ Some of the alternative theoretical explanations were not supported by the empirical analysis, and none of the eight alternative models of the robustness check yields a better overall fit of the estimated model in the context of our sample (Benitez et al., 2020b). In this sense, we can conclude that none of these alternative models provide a better theoretical model to explain how social media capability and business analytics talent function in companies and help them to create business value. The results of the estimation of these eight alternative models provide additional robustness and credibility to the findings of our study.

big data analytics have a positive interaction effect on market performance, which is more salient for small than for large firms. Our findings are consistent with Dong and Yang's (2020) work. We argue and find that business analytics talent is a valuable IT resource that helps firms to convert the unstructured social data (captured through social media capability) in useful new knowledge to be explored, shared, and stored. In this sense, the empirical analysis supports our proposed research model.

Based on the test of robustness, we obtained additional results on how knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation (driven by social media capability and amplified by business analytics talent) affect firm performance. Both exploration and exploitation have been found to help firms to increase their business benefits. Organizational knowledge is a resource difficult to imitate, which may be a source of competitive advantage (Alavi and Leidner, 2001). As an illustrative example of the role of social media and knowledge management in improving firm performance, Dell created a social media platform (<http://www.ideastorm.com/>) to acquire and exploit social data from their customers, enabling them to submit their ideas, vote for other ideas, and comment on ideas of other customers. Dell managed customers' data to implement the best ideas (e.g., biodegradable packing material), which led to higher firm performance. In this sense, an effective exploration and exploitation of knowledge provide an excellent return on investment for a firm (Dong and Wu, 2015). Indeed, our results suggest that knowledge exploitation has a greater effect on firm performance than knowledge exploration does, which is rational and consistent with prior IS research (Benitez et al., 2018d). The acquisition and creation of new knowledge are related to sensing of new business opportunities (Benitez et al., 2018d; Cui et al., 2019) and affect firm performance. However, the biggest effect on firm performance will be produced once the company assimilates, uses, and exploits the knowledge, which is related to the exploitation of business opportunities. Therefore, it is rational to think that the effect of usage, leveraging, and application of knowledge (knowledge exploitation) on firm performance is greater than the creation, sharing, and storage of knowledge (knowledge exploration).

5.2. Key contributions to IS research

This study draws on the business value of social media and knowledge management IS literature to link social media capability and a firm's knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. This paper contributes to the IS research in three ways. First, although the crucial challenge for organizations is to learn how they can develop the ability of effectively selecting, using, and leveraging external social media to scan, learn, and internalize knowledge, it remains rather unclear how companies can develop a social media capability and create business value from this capability. Instead, prior IS research has focused on understanding the knowledge sharing behavior of employees in enterprise social media (e.g., Beck et al., 2014; Leonardi), user-generated content and customer engagement to diffuse information through social media (e.g., Bapna et al., 2019). In a different way of prior IS research on this topic that has emphasized on the employee, customer, and user as a unit of analysis, we focus on the organizational level. We develop the concept of social media capability, explain it theoretically, provide a set of measures that can be built with archival data, and show empirical evidence on how firms can explore and exploit knowledge from social media. This is the first primary contribution of this manuscript to IS research.

Second, although the firm's business analytics talent may perform a critical role in understanding and acquire new knowledge from big customer data in social media, this plausible effect was under-theorized in IS research. Instead, prior IS research has focused on the impact of big data analytics capability on competitive performance (Mikalef et al., 2020) and its reinforcing role to create synergies and improves market performance (Dong and Yang, 2020). However, it exists an overemphasis on the analytics software and a minimization of the role of analytics talent and people (Conboy et al., 2020). Drawn from the managerial paper of Ransbotham et al. (2015), we develop the concept and measure of business analytics talent, and shows how this resource reinforces the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration. This study suggests that business analytics talent is a complementary resource of social media capability

since they mutually reinforce in such a way that the presence of business analytics talent amplifies the impact of social media capability on knowledge exploration. Thus, business analytics talent enables firms to better explore new knowledge from external social media. We also build and propose a measure of business analytics talent that has been supported by the empirical analysis, and that can be used in future impactful IS research. This is the second contribution of this paper to the discipline of IS.

Finally, our study aimed to confirm the proposed research model by using consistent estimates. For this reason, we used the PLS estimator and the ADANCO software statistical package. Both IS research and PLS path modeling requires the usage of the most-up-to-date statistical standards. By using ADANCO, this paper illustrates how to run a confirmatory composite analysis to check if the structure of measures is correct. Besides, it shows how to check if the proposed research model is correct by evaluating the overall fit of the estimated model. This last illustration is also presented for eight alternative models that are included in a test of robustness. As the final contribution to IS research, this paper introduces the ADANCO software package, recommends its usage for future confirmatory IS research, and illustrates it in a study on the business value of social media capability.

5.3. Limitations and avenues for future IS research

This paper also has some limitations, which also suggest excellent avenues for further IS research. First, these results can only be generalized to small firms in the U.S. market. Future IS research could investigate whether the proposed research model is also supported in different geographic markets and larger companies. Second, we restricted our focus to a limited number of external social media platforms. This approach implies that the effects explored by this study on knowledge exploration and exploitation can only be associated with the firm's external social media. Although we examined three of the most popular external social media platforms (Braojos et al., 2019; Culnan et al., 2010), our research does not explore enterprise/internal social media platforms (e.g., Microsoft Yammer, Facebook Workplace) and other emerging external social media platforms

(e.g., Instagram, LinkedIn). Moreover, cultural differences may influence how firms leverage social media capability and business analytics talent. We encourage IS scholars to investigate these potential differences in future IS studies. For instance, how the external social media platforms used by Chinese firms (e.g., WeChat) and the digital ecosystem of Chinese firms/customers are different from those used by U.S. firms/customers could be an interesting topic for future impactful IS research. Further, IS research can extend this study by examining enterprise social media platforms and other new external social media platforms and including them in the conceptualization of social media capability. Third, we are confident about the ingredients used to assess Facebook capability, Twitter capability, and blog capability are a good proxy to evaluate these constructs, which has also been supported by the confirmatory composite analysis. However, we recognize that our measurements of these constructs may present some “noise” between the conceptualization and the measurements, which usually happens when a study uses secondary data. Future IS research could develop perceptual measures for social media capability and validate them through a confirmatory composite/factor analysis. This future IS research will be valuable and will offer the opportunity to replicate the results of our study.

Fourth, the development of social media capability and its exploitation to create business value may be contingent on the social media governance mechanisms implemented by the firm. How should the firm’s governance structure be to maximize the value creation from social media? Future IS research should theorize and empirically examine the effects of social media governance mechanisms on the business value of social media. This seems an excellent research topic to explore in future IS research. Fifth, we find a greater effect of social media capability on knowledge exploration than on knowledge exploitation. This result invites to theorize that firms may need other organizational capabilities acting as mediators or moderators in the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploitation. We encourage IS scholars interested in this research topic to theorize and investigate these organizational capabilities that can enable the exploitation of existing knowledge. Finally, this study conceptualizes and finds discriminant validity

between social media capability and business analytics talent. However, some IS scholars may consider that these concepts are closely related or even be part of each other if they focus on a more general concept such as IT-enabled information management capability. We run a call for knowledge discovery and addressing this debate, which is another exciting avenue for IS research. Who wishes to take the relay?

5.4. Key lessons learned for IT and business executives

The findings of this study also provide important lessons learned for IT and business executives. First, developing social media capability enables firms to explore and exploit knowledge. The executives should be aware of the potential benefits associated with the usage of external social media to acquire customer, competitor, and supplier data. Companies can also use social media to promote their products and initiatives to collect valuable opinions, preferences, suggestions for improvement, ideas from customers and suppliers, and competitor's strategic information. Social media can also be leveraged to co-create knowledge with customers and suppliers. Thus, this study suggests that managers should invest, deploy, and leverage social media to acquire and exploit knowledge. For example, Grupo Expansion (a leading Mexican holding of the communication industry) has the capacity to use external social media (e.g., Facebook, Twitter) to touch potential customers, run marketing campaigns, and acquire knowledge from current customers and competitors, thus enabling the exploration of new knowledge (Hootsuite, 2020b).

Second, firms can amplify the impact of social media capability on knowledge exploration if they recruit, develop, and retain business analytics talent. This study shows evidence on how strategic will become to win the war for top tech talent. Executives should be aware of the importance of having business analytics specialized staff, keeping in mind the expected shortage of this talent in the market. Business analytics talent is scarce in the market. Companies should go the extra mile in attracting, retaining, and developing business analytics specialists (e.g., developing an outstanding employer branding), and training those with high potential. Business analytics talented firms can benefit from social media at a higher level since social media

capability, and business analytics talent reinforce each other to obtain better new knowledge exploration. To the extent the new knowledge created and captured today will be the base of the future firm's exploitation activities, this new knowledge will ensure the exploitation and firm's survival in the future. Grupo Expansion also has business analytics talent to use analytics to convert external social media data into useful new knowledge. They use Hootsuite Analytics to assess social media metrics (e.g., number of followers and clicks, customer engagement) to better create content and acquire customer knowledge. Andrea Sanchez's (Senior Specialist of Digital Products of Grupo Expansion) statement is consistent with our findings: "Analytics helps our team to convert data into useful information and specific recommendations. Our digital team can make strategic decisions based on business intelligence, and we are obtaining business benefits" (Hootsuite, 2020b, p. 3).

5.4. Core conclusions

Social media are one of the disruptive IT resources to transform the company digitally, build a seamless digital business strategy, and survive in the long-run in the digital disruption era. This manuscript proposed a research model on social media capability, knowledge exploration, knowledge exploitation, and business analytics talent. We found that social media capability enables firms to explore new knowledge and exploit existing knowledge. We also discovered that business analytics talent reinforces the relationship between social media capability and knowledge exploration. Social media data have become a gold mine for business intelligence, but companies need business analytics talent to discover new useful knowledge. By drawing on the lens of knowledge exploration and exploitation and business analytics talent, we offer a new theoretical explanation to the IS research community by investigating the business value of social media through knowledge exploration and exploitation. Of course, IT does matter. Quo Vadis? (Palvia et al., 2020).

This paper has the potential to change some of the existing paradigms in IS research, potentially in two possible directions. The first potential change may be methodological. The current scenario of IS research provides us the opportunity to build innovative datasets and search for confirmatory IS research. We hope this study inspires other IS scholars by using our secondary data-based measurements and test their consistency and adequacy through an overall fit evaluation of the saturated model. Similarly, this study shows that IS research can confirm the proposed research model through the overall fit evaluation of the estimated model. We introduce the ADANCO software package, explains why to use it, and illustrate how to use it for confirmatory IS research in the research stream of the business value of IT. The second potential change is related to digital capabilities. The design and execution of digital transformation strategies have become “a must” for companies. This strategic imperative has been accelerated with the COVID-19 pandemic. The coming future will provide firms the opportunity to explore new digital resources that will require new digital firm’s capabilities. These new digital capabilities (e.g., leveraging artificial intelligence, 5G, blockchain) have the potential to serve business activities and maximize business benefits. Many of these new digital capabilities will need to be conceptualized and tested empirically isolated from prior IT capabilities, as it was done in this study with social media capability and business analytics talent. We hope this paper also inspires others in this direction. “I do not do fashion. I am fashion” (Coco Channel). Similarly, IS research does not do fashionable research. IS research is fashion. Future paradigms in IS research can be “unframed thinking.”

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7. Appendix

Table A1: Prior IS research on social media and knowledge management

Authors	Study title	Journal	Research goal	Key findings
Bapna et al. (2019)	Nurturing online communities: An empirical investigation	<i>MIS Quarterly</i>	Understanding the effect of participation of firms in online communities on customer engagement	Firm's posts in online communities interact with customers and are diffused by customers with other users which diffuse the firm's information and increase customer engagement
Song et al. (2019)	Impact of the usage of social media in the workplace on team and employee performance	<i>Information & Management</i>	Analyzing the impact of the usage of social media in the workplace on team and employee performance	Work-oriented social media (DingTalk) and socialization-oriented social media (WeChat) are complementary resources that generate synergies to improve team and employee performance
Yang et al. (2019)	Understanding user-generated content and customer engagement on Facebook business pages	<i>Information Systems Research</i>	To examine the antecedents and effects of user content generation in the Facebook business page	The negative customer posts are significantly more prevalent than positive posts. They observed three types of customer complaints related to product quality, money issues, and social and environmental issues. They found that social complaints receive more likes, but fewer comments, than quality or money complaints
Davison et al. (2018)	Interpersonal knowledge exchange in China: The impact of guanxi and social media	<i>Information & Management</i>	To understand the interpersonal knowledge exchange in China	The guanxi lubricates the social media-based communication practices that are central to interpersonal knowledge exchange in China

Fang et al. (2018)	Not all posts are treated equal: An empirical investigation of post replying behavior in an online travel community	<i>Information & Management</i>	To investigate the knowledge sharing behavior in an online travel community	Sharing post length and vividness, contributors' expertise and degree centrality, and members' social interactions have significant associations with the number of replying posts in an online travel community
Gunarathne et al. (2018)	When social media delivers customer service: Differential customer treatment in the airline industry	<i>MIS Quarterly</i>	To examine when social media affect customer service	Airlines companies respond to half of the Twitter-based customer complaints in comparison with the expected full response to the complaints in traditional call centers. These companies respond to complaints on Twitter from customers with more followers
Neely and Leonardi (2018)	Enacting knowledge strategy through social media: Passable trust and the paradox of nonwork interactions	<i>Strategic Management Journal</i>	Investigating the effect of the employee's usage of social media on the online and offline knowledge exchange between employees	Employees use social media to exchange work and nonwork contents. These interactions affect the curiosity and passable trust between employees, but also provoke tensions between them, which it affects to their knowledge sharing
Van Osch and Steinfield (2018)	Strategic visibility in enterprise social media: Implications for network formation and boundary spanning	<i>Journal of Management Information Systems</i>	To explore the effect of enterprise social media-driven visibility on the network formation and boundary spanning	The enterprise social media-driven visibility facilitates organizational members to be involved in diverse network structures, which in turn have implications for distinct boundary-spanning activities
Gunarathne et al. (2017)	Whose and what social media complaints have happier resolutions? Evidence from twitter	<i>Journal of Management Information Systems</i>	To understand whose and what complaints on social media are likely to have happier resolutions	They find those complaining customers who are more influential in Twitter are more likely to be satisfied
Pan et al. (2015)	Integrating social networking support for dyadic knowledge exchange: A study in a virtual community of practice	<i>Information & Management</i>	Understanding the role of social media in the effect of virtual communities of practice on knowledge exchange	The integration of social media on a virtual community of practice facilitates the knowledge exchange between friends
Beck et al. (2014)	Knowledge exchange and symbolic action in social media-enabled electronic networks of practice: A multilevel perspective on knowledge seekers and contributors	<i>MIS Quarterly</i>	To investigate the impact of enterprise social media on knowledge sharing between employees	Knowledge seekers' characteristics and relational factors drive knowledge exchanges in social media-enabled electronic networks of practice. The communicative act expressed by question-answer pairs impacts the quality of knowledge exchanged between employees in enterprise social media
Kane et al. (2014b)	What's different about social media networks? A framework and research agenda	<i>MIS Quarterly</i>	To establish a framework and research agenda for social media networks	They distinguish between online and offline social media networks and discuss the implications for the social network analysis. They

				also propose a framework and research agenda for social media networks
Leonardi (2014)	Social media, knowledge sharing, and innovation: Toward a theory of communication visibility	<i>Information Systems Research</i>	Examining the effect of enterprise social media on knowledge sharing of employees and the firm's innovation	Enterprise social media increase the visibility of the communication among organizational members and facilitate the meta-knowledge (understanding who knows what and whom). Enterprise social media change the way organizational members share knowledge, which can facilitate the development of new products
Mount and Garcia (2014)	Rejuvenating a brand through social media	<i>MIT Sloan Management Review</i>	Understanding the impact of social media firm's usage on the brand rejuvenating	Nestle UK used Facebook and YouTube to rejuvenate its Kit Kat brand. They scanned the insights and opinions of customers, and engaged customers (increased interest in the brand). After that, Nestle UK learned and internalized the customer big data to increase market penetration by 8%
Chau and Xu (2012)	Business intelligence in blogs: Understanding consumer interactions and communities	<i>MIS Quarterly</i>	To study how blogs can be used by users to generate contents and by companies as a source of business intelligence	They propose an organizational and managerial framework to effectively collect, extract, and analyze blogs related to the topics of interest, reveal novel patterns in the blogger interactions and communities, and answer important business intelligence questions
Chai et al. (2011)	Factors affecting bloggers' knowledge sharing: An investigation across gender	<i>Journal of Management Information Systems</i>	Understanding the factors affecting knowledge sharing of bloggers	Bloggers' trust, the strength of social ties, and reciprocity all have a positive effect on their knowledge-sharing behavior. The impact of each factor on such behavior varies by gender
Faraj et al. (2011)	Knowledge collaboration in online communities	<i>Organization Science</i>	Exploring the knowledge collaboration of individuals in online communities	The fluidity of the online communities affects the resources and the dynamic of knowledge collaboration among organizational members